

MEDICAL SCIENCES

NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION BETWEEN PATIENTS AND OPHTHALMOLOGISTS IN OUTPATIENT MEDICAL CARE

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Abstract

Non-verbal communication has gained a crucial role in the work of medical specialists. Through it they address concrete, communicative messages to the patients in a variety of ways, not only through the medium of speech but also through body language. This article presents and analyses the meaning of the non-verbal elements of the communication between patients and ophthalmologists. The opinions of patients as to how they understand the non-verbal elements of communication with the physician and their preferred distance between the participants were both studied. The influence of respondent age on the non-verbal element they prioritise and on the significance of correspondent distance for good communication has been presented herein.

Keywords: communication, non-verbal elements, ophthalmologist, patient

Medical specialists address concrete, communicative messages in a variety of ways, not only through their speech but also through body language. In the process of providing medical care and health care, non-verbal signals become crucial as they can complement or downplay, reinforce, diminish or change the meaning of verbal messages. This is determined to a large extent by the patient's hypersensitivity as a person experiencing pain, fear, anxiety and uncertainty [1, 2, 3, 4].

The goal of this article is to explore and present the importance of non-verbal elements in the communication between patients and outpatient ophthalmologists.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks have been completed:

1. Presenting non-verbal communication skills that play a crucial role in healthcare.
2. Studying patient's opinions on how they understand the non-verbal elements of communication with the ophthalmologist, namely voice intonation, facial expression, body movements, eye contact.
3. The impact of the respondent age on the non-verbal element they favour.
4. Studying and analysing the significance of preferred space between the participants in the communication.
5. Formulating conclusions about the role of nonverbal communication in outpatient ophthalmology practice.

Material and methods.

The documentary and the questionnaire method were used to objectify the results observed. Sources in the field of non-verbal communication have been studied.

A questionnaire survey was conducted in Sofia during the 01.02.2021-31.01.2022 period. Its goal was examining and analyzing the patients' opinions on the significance of non-verbal communication with specialists in outpatient care (ophthalmologists). A total of

516 patients have participated to the questionnaire after visiting an ophthalmologist in specialised outpatient care during the period listed.

The selection is random - no selection of the respondents has occurred, which is sufficient basis to claim that the results are representative. The confidence interval at significance level $P(t)=0.05$ provides information, which can be used to assess the accuracy of the analysed indicators.

The quantitative analyses have been performed with the SPSS 17.0 statistical software package. MICROSOFT OFFICE products have been used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

Results and discussion.

Non-verbal communication skills are defined as the ability to be aware of, master and control over 800 000 non-verbal signals. The ones that play the most important role in healthcare, according to V. Tacheva's research are the following [3]:

Body language: body posture; kinetic signs of the head, the body, the hands and the feet; facial expressions; smiling; lip, eye and eyebrow movements.

Spatio-temporal and tactile signals: distance; behaviour and movement in space; physical contact with patients (shaking hands, touching, physical manipulation, performing instrumental examination, palpation, percussion, massage, etc.)

Cultural, social, and personal non-verbal signs of related to civilization - the medic's appearance: clothing and footwear: style of dress appropriate to the specific medical activity; type, quality and cleanliness of clothing (uniform); the hairstyle, beard and moustache; the hygiene of the body, hands, hair and oral cavity; cosmetics, perfume, make-up, manicure, tattoos; wearing a limited number of accessories (watches, bracelets and rings, chains, necklaces, earrings, piercings) that would not interfere with professional activities.

Professional and psychological non-verbal signs: demonstrating a willingness to listen; providing conditions for privacy and the sharing of personal, intimate

or delicate facts; taking enough time for explanations, for answering reasonable questions, for giving more information, for performing the procedure, manipulation, activity; the mood of the health professional; the attitude towards the patient.

Non-verbal signals of the hospital environment and setting; the overall appearance of the medical facility; the availability of a website with visuals and data of importance to patients; the provision of information (visual, verbal, graphical, statistical, etc.) about the medical activities performed and the clinical pathways serviced in the health facility and in each of its units (clinic, ward, section, sector); the availability of information boards, diagrams, instructions, directions about the structure, conditions; the quality and reliability of medical equipment for diagnosis and treatment; the provision of timely information about prices, methods

and terms of payment; the furnishings and furniture in offices, manipulation rooms, hospital rooms; comfortable seating and examination spaces, wheelchairs for severely ill patients and patients with mobility difficulties; the size, hygiene and general appearance of the medical care rooms; seating and examination spaces, wheelchairs for the severely ill and patients with mobility difficulties; the size, hygiene and general appearance of the medical care room; the lighting and window shading; the heating, cooling, ventilation systems; having a quiet and peaceful environment during examinations and procedures; providing comfortable facilities for the collection of blood, urine, etc. having comfortable and constantly functioning lifts for the patients and their relatives; having technical equipment in good working order - computer, printer.

Figure 1. Age structure of the patients surveyed

In order to research and analyze the significance of non-verbal elements in patient-physician communication, we developed a questionnaire for patients visiting an ophthalmologist in specialised outpatient care. The patients' responses were collected after a visit to the physician during the period of the questionnaire.

The gender distribution of the patients in the survey was 58.2% women and 41.8% men. The age structure of the respondents is presented in Figure 1. The age characteristics of the respondents are studied in order to satisfy the needs of the study and so as to compare the

age indicator with other indicators tracked in the research.

In order to research the place of non-verbal elements in the communication between the patients and their ophthalmologist, we asked the respondents the following question: "Do you pay attention to non-verbal elements when communicating with your ophthalmologist?". The results show that the majority of respondents (88.7%) pay attention to the nonverbal elements in communication with the physician (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution frequency of participants concerning the significance for non-verbal elements in communicating with the ophthalmologist

In order to determine the most commonly used non-verbal elements in communicating with the physician, we asked the following survey question. Respond-

ents attributed the greatest significance in communication to their interlocutor's intonation - 35.6%, followed by facial expression - 24.3%, and eye contact - 21.7% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Distribution frequency of the respondents according to the non-verbal elements most frequently used in the communicative act

We identified an that the age of the respondents has an influence on their non-verbal element they prioritise. Respondents under the age of thirty and over the age of sixty were most likely to prioritize eye contact,

33.2% and 35.8%, respectively. Meanwhile, respondents between the ages of thirty and forty prioritized facial expression (33.1%) and voice intonation (43.7%), and patients between the ages of forty and fifty placed the most importance on intonation (38.3%) (Table 1).

Table 1.

The influence of age on the respondents' opinions on the most frequently used non-verbal elements in communication

ELEMENTS OF NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION	AGE GROUPS				
	under 30	30-40	40-50	50-60	over 60.
intonation	19.9%	43.7%	38.3%	17.7%	18.1%
facial expression	12.1%	33.1%	20.1%	13.6%	17.1%
eye contact	33.2%	7.1%	9.1%	8.7%	35.8%
body movements	8.8%	6.7%	3.9%	10.5%	12.3%
all of the above	2.2%	2.4%	4.3%	37.8%	2.4%
No	20.2%	5.2%	18.2%	7.3%	8.3%
I cannot assess	3.6%	1.8%	6.1%	4.4%	6.0%

In the group of respondents aged between fifty and sixty, all of the following elements of non-verbal communication were prioritized (37.8%). The largest portion of patients who do not prioritize nonverbal methods (20.2%) in communication is in the group of respondents under the age of thirty (Table 1).

Another research question we studied was the typical distance between the patients and the physician at

the moment of communication, as distance is an especially important component of communication.

The results show that more than half of the respondents (58.7%) prefer to be within one meter of the physician when communicating, while 34.5% of all the survey participants prefer to be between one and two meters away (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Distribution frequency of respondents according to preferred distance between the participants in the communication act

In order to find out whether the distance between the interlocutors is important for good communication, we asked the following question in our survey. The results show that the majority of the patients surveyed

(78.5%) attribute significance to distance in communication with the ophthalmologist, and for 16.8% of them, the distance between interlocutors in communication is not important (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Distribution frequency of respondents according to their opinion on the significance of distance between interlocutors for good communication

The participants' age has an influence over their opinion on the research question. Among the respondents under the age of thirty, the largest number (53.5%) are those who do not attach importance to the distance between them and the physician with whom they speak. Among respondents aged between thirty and forty, this

percentage begins to fall, with about a third of them (35.8%) sharing the same opinion.

In the group of respondents aged between forty and fifty, distance appears to be a prioritised (64.3%). Most of the respondents for whom distance is an important element of communication are in the group of respondents aged over sixty (76.6%) (Table 2).

Table 2

The influence of age on the respondents' opinions regarding the significance of distance between interlocutors for good communication.

the significance of correspondent distance for good communication	AGE GROUPS				
	under 30	30 - 40	40 - 50	50 - 60	over 60 years
yes	28.7%	45.1%	64.3%	67.7%	76.6%
no	53.5%	35.8%	25.0%	18.6%	12.2%
I cannot assess	17,8%	19.1%	10.7%	13.7%	11.2%

Based on the analysis of the patients' opinions on the role of non-verbal components in their communication with ophthalmologists in outpatient specialised care, the following conclusions can be drawn:

6. The majority of patients surveyed (88.7%) paid attention to the non-verbal elements in their communication with the physician. They seem to attribute the greatest significance to the intonation of their interlocutor (35.6%), followed by the facial expression (24.3%) and eye contact (21.7%).

7. More than half of the questionnaire participants (58.7%) prefer the distance between them and the physician to be up to one meter.

8. The study has established that the age of the respondents has an influence on their non-verbal communication element they prioritise and on their opinion on the significance of the distance between them and the physician with whom they are speaking.

Conclusion

Non-verbal communication in the process of interactions between patients and outpatient physicians warrants considerable attention, as it is one of the conditions for patient satisfaction with the healthcare services provided. Medical professionals develop their non-verbal communication skills throughout their con-

scious life and those skills depend on a variety of factors, which is why it is necessary to study and analyse them.

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